

THE EFFECT OF DISCOUNTS, BRAND IMAGE, AND BRAND TRUST ON CONSUMER SATISFACTION AT MATAHARI DEPARTMENT STORE IN PALU CITY

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Received : 15 January 2026

Accepted : 25 January 2026

Revised : 01 February 2026

Published : 20 March 2026

Abstract

This study aims to analyze the influence of discounts, *brand image*, and *brand trust* on consumer satisfaction at Matahari Department Store in Palu City. This study uses a quantitative approach with a survey method by distributing questionnaires to 96 respondents who are consumers of Matahari Department Store in Palu City. The results of the study indicate that Discounts, *Brand Image*, and *Brand Trust* partially have a positive and significant influence on consumer satisfaction. In addition, the three variables simultaneously also have a positive and significant influence on consumer satisfaction. This finding emphasizes the importance of an integrated marketing strategy that combines attractive price promotions (discounts), the formation of a strong and positive brand image, and high brand trust to increase overall consumer satisfaction and support business sustainability in the retail industry, especially Matahari Department Store.

Keywords: *Discount, Brand Image, Brand Trust, Consumer Satisfaction, Matahari Department Store*

INTRODUCTION

In today's increasingly competitive retail business, customer satisfaction is a key factor in maintaining customer loyalty and increasing company competitiveness. Retail business encompasses all business activities related to sales and service delivery to consumers for personal and family use. Retail businesses are also known as retail businesses because products are typically sold in single units and the marketing target of these retail businesses is the end consumer (Bahri, 2018). This makes retail a rapidly growing business, characterized by the enthusiasm and aggressiveness of economic actors in the industrial, service, and trade sectors. Matahari Department Store is one of the oldest and largest retail companies in Indonesia. Matahari Department Store opened its first store as a children's clothing store on October 24, 1958, in the Pasar Baru area of Jakarta. Matahari provides a variety of fashion products, such as clothing, shoes, accessories, and bags, with a focus on quality, fashionable, and affordable products for the growing middle class consumers in Indonesia. It is no wonder that Matahari has become the first choice for most people in Indonesia when it comes to fulfilling their fashion needs.

Matahari Department Store has built a reputation as a family shopping center with a complete range of products under one roof, while also contributing to local economic growth through job creation and support for local suppliers. As its business grows, Matahari Department Store understands the importance of customer satisfaction as a key to the company's success and sustainability. In this regard, efforts to increase customer satisfaction not only focus on product quality, but also on effective marketing strategies such as providing discounts, creating a positive brand image, and *building brand trust*. This study selected Matahari Department Store in Palu City as the research object because this store represents the characteristics of a dynamic and rapidly growing regional retail market, but still faces high competition from other retail stores. Furthermore, Matahari has a broad and diverse customer base, making it a relevant location to examine consumer behavior towards implemented marketing strategies. Sihura et al (2023) defines customer satisfaction as the fulfillment of customer desires, expectations, and needs. Satisfying customers means providing accurate information and plans, identifying customer problems, and providing appropriate services and solutions (Bachri et al, 2023). If these needs are met or even exceeded, the individual will feel satisfied. Conversely, if needs are not met, dissatisfaction will arise. Customer satisfaction is a feeling of pleasure or displeasure that arises after consumers compare the performance received with their desired expectations (Efendi et al, 2023). Customer satisfaction plays a crucial role for companies because when consumers are satisfied,

companies have the potential to gain benefits in the form of increased profits and strengthen customer loyalty to their products or services. The variable of customer satisfaction was chosen as the dependent variable because satisfaction is a key indicator of a company's success in retaining customers and increasing competitiveness. The purpose of measuring customer satisfaction is to gather information, both regarding what customers say about things that need to be changed, and to evaluate how well the company meets its current customer needs. (Zahara, 2022) . The higher the level of customer satisfaction, the higher the level of customer loyalty (Hidayah & Nugroho, 2023) . The selection of the customer satisfaction variable in this study is also based on the characteristics of the retail industry, such as Matahari Department Store, which relies heavily on the customer experience during shopping. Therefore, companies cannot ignore efforts to maintain and improve customer satisfaction.

Offering discounts is a frequently used marketing strategy, not only contributing to increased sales but also influencing consumer perceptions and satisfaction with the products or services offered. According to Sari et al. (2023) , a discount is a price reduction offered by a seller to a buyer, or a direct reduction in the price of a product for a specific period. Meanwhile, according to Setiawan (2024) , a discount is a price reduction offered by a seller to a buyer after a transaction has taken place. Offering discounts also plays a crucial role in increasing consumer satisfaction because when customers receive a discount, they perceive an additional benefit, meaning greater economic value, from the transaction. The discount variable was chosen because it is one of the most effective promotional strategies for influencing consumer behavior in the retail sector. Discounts benefit consumers by reducing their expenses, leading to greater satisfaction, as they obtain products at more affordable prices. (Latifah & Nurmalasari, 2023) . In a modern retail context like Matahari Department Store, discount programs are one of the most frequently implemented forms of promotion, such as *seasonal sales* , *clearance sales* , or special member discounts. Therefore, the discount variable was chosen because it has strong relevance in directly influencing consumer perceptions of value and satisfaction.

Brand *image* plays a crucial role in influencing consumer satisfaction and how consumers evaluate a brand. Laraswati & Harti (2022) define *brand image* as the consumer's perception or view of a brand, with the company's goal being to build a positive impression in the minds of its customers. Meanwhile, according to Rehansyah & Simatupang (2023), brand image is defined as: Brand image is the beliefs and impressions consumers have of a product or company, which remain embedded and remembered in their minds . This opinion reflects how consumers view and evaluate the brand based on their experiences, information, and perceptions. *The brand image variable* was chosen because it is a crucial element in shaping consumer perceptions of a brand's quality, credibility, and reputation. A good brand image can create emotional value for consumers, which will create positive feelings when purchasing or using the brand (Apriany et al., 2022) . This is important because brand image not only shapes consumer perceptions but also plays a role in determining the level of satisfaction they feel after consuming a product or service. In the retail world, consumers not only consider price but also brand reputation and perception as a basis for making purchasing decisions. Matahari Department Store has an image as a large, modern, and trusted retail brand, making *brand image* an important variable to study because it can determine the level of consumer satisfaction.

Brand trust is an important continuation after brand image in building long-term relationships with consumers. Brand trust is the belief in a brand that can be relied upon (brand reliability) to fulfill promises made to consumers, and is perceived to have positive intentions (*brand intention*) rooted in consumers' perceptions that the brand prioritizes important things that align with their needs and desires (Gultom & Fadli, 2024) . This trust is formed through repeated interactions between consumers and brands that result in positive experiences and the absence of significant disappointment. Lindawaty et al (2022) argue that brand trust is a feeling of security obtained by consumers in their interactions with a brand based on the perception that the brand is reliable and meets consumers' interests and safety. Excellent brand trust will be the key to a brand's success because the more consumers trust a brand, the higher the level of consumer satisfaction with the product sold. *The brand trust variable* was chosen because trust in a brand is the main foundation in long-term relationships between consumers and companies. Good trust in a brand is crucial to determining the brand's success, because consumer trust in a brand is proportional to the level of consumer satisfaction (Syanjari & Argo, 2024) . In a retail context like Matahari Department Store, trust in product authenticity, product quality, and service are crucial factors in determining whether consumers feel safe and comfortable continuing to shop. Therefore, brand trust was chosen because it significantly influences consumers' sense of security, confidence, and ultimately, satisfaction. Previous research generally only examines the effect of discounts, *brand image*, or *brand trust* on consumer satisfaction separately or only combines two variables in one research model. Still few studies analyze these three variables simultaneously within an integrated research framework. Therefore, this study was conducted to fill this gap by analyzing the influence of discounts, brand image, and brand trust simultaneously on consumer satisfaction. The researcher conducted this study because consumer

satisfaction is a key factor in increasing the competitiveness of retail businesses. This study aims to find out, analyze, and empirically test the influence of these three factors so that the company can optimize its marketing strategy to increase consumer satisfaction, especially at Matahari Department Store in Palu City.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Customer Satisfaction

Consumer satisfaction according to Wijaya et al (2023) is a person's feeling after comparing their expectations with what they receive, if the results exceed expectations, then consumers feel satisfied. . Meanwhile, according to Palelu et al (2022) Satisfaction is a person's feeling of pleasure or disappointment that arises after comparing the performance or results of a product that is expected. If performance matches or even exceeds expectations, consumers will feel happy or satisfied, conversely, if performance is below expectations, consumers will feel disappointed or dissatisfied (Prasetiyo et al, 2022) . According to Hamzah & Ariesta (2022:29) the dimensions of consumer satisfaction are: Product quality, price, service quality, emotional factors, and convenience.

Discount

According to Damayanti & Damayanti (2024) , a discount is a price reduction below the standard price given for a certain period of time. According to Awaliyah et al. (2023) , a discount is a reduction in the price of a product from the normal price within a certain period to increase sales volume. Providing timely and measured discounts can provide benefits not only for sellers but also for consumers, because consumers get products at more affordable prices. According to Baskara (2018:89) , the dimensions of a discount are: the amount of the price reduction, the time of the price reduction, and the type of product & payment method.

Brand Image

Brand image is defined as consumer perception and preference for a brand, as reflected by various brand associations in consumer memory (Mahendri & Munir, 2021) . According to Sampe & Tahalele (2023), brand image ADDIN ZOTERO_ITEM CSL_CITATION {"citationID":"eFlymctv","properties":{"formattedCitation":"(Sampe & Tahalele, 2023 This study aims to examine and analyze the influence of brand image and product quality on purchasing decisions for VIVO brand smartphones at the Bandung Jaya A. Y. Patty Ambon store. Data collection was carried out by distributing questionnaires to respondents and after that it was tested and analyzed using SPSS software version 21.0. According to the results of data processing, it can be concluded that the characteristics of respondents based on age are mostly 19 year old respondents with a percentage of 19%, while the characteristics of respondents based on work are mostly students with a percentage of 57%. Based on the test results of the coefficient of determination (R²) shows that 0.733 or about 73.3% of the purchasing decision variables can be influenced or explained by brand image and product quality variables, while the other 26.7% are influenced or explained by other variables not discussed in this study is the association that arises in consumers' minds when recalling a particular brand. By understanding the associations that arise in consumers' minds, companies can design appropriate brand messages and experiences to strengthen positive images and effectively manage negative perceptions. Products with a stronger brand image can be perceived by consumers as products of superior quality and value (Alfian & Nainggolan, 2022) . According to Keller & Swaminathan (2020:239), the dimensions of *brand image* are: *Brand strength* , *Brand favorability* , and *Brand uniqueness* .

Brand Trust

According to Hastari et al (2023) *Brand Trust* is a consumer's belief that a company is reliable and offers services and products with promising quality. Nurfitriah et al. (2023) also argue that Brand Trust is a consumer's view of a brand's reliability, which is formed from various transactions or interactions that demonstrate the fulfillment of expectations regarding product performance and consumer loyalty. Brand trust refers to consumer confidence in a brand's reputation (Tria & Syah, 2021) . Consumers with a high level of trust will feel safe and confident that the goods or services offered can meet their long-term needs. According to Ika & Kustini in (Suntoro & Silintowe, 2020:28) *Dimension of Viability*, and *Dimension of Intentionality*.

HYPOTHESIS DEVELOPMENT

This research is based on previous theories and findings that examine the relationship between discounts, *brand image* , and *brand trust* on customer satisfaction at Matahari Department Store. Discounts not only attract consumers' attention to purchase products but also provide a perception of economic benefits that increase

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satisfaction with the transaction. Research by Simanungkalit et al. (2022) shows that discounts influence customer satisfaction. A positive brand image will create emotional value and consumer confidence in making purchases, thereby increasing satisfaction. Research by Ferdiansa et al. (2022) shows that *brand image* influences customer satisfaction. Consumer trust in a brand will create a sense of security, reduce risk, and increase satisfaction. Research by Ihsan & Sutedjo (2022) shows that brand trust influences customer satisfaction. Discounts, *brand image*, and *brand trust* are important factors that can simultaneously influence the level of customer satisfaction. These three variables complement each other in creating a valuable shopping experience for customers. Discounts create a perception of economic gain and increase financial satisfaction. A positive *brand image fosters emotional perceptions and brand pride*. *Brand trust*, on the other hand, strengthens consumers' sense of security and confidence in the brand's quality and commitment to meeting their needs. Therefore, the hypothesis in this study is:

H1 : Discounts have an effect on consumer satisfaction

H2 : *Brand image* influences consumer satisfaction

H3 : *Brand trust* has an effect on consumer satisfaction

H4 : Discounts, *brand image*, and *brand trust* have an influence on consumer satisfaction.

Information :

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study uses a quantitative approach. In this study, the independent variables are discounts, *brand image*, and *brand trust*, and the dependent variable is consumer satisfaction. This study was conducted at Matahari Department Store. The data collection method for this study was offline with a direct survey technique conducted by distributing questionnaires filled out by respondents in physical form. The population in this study were all Matahari Department Store consumers in Palu City. The sampling technique used was non-probability sampling using purposive sampling, namely sampling carried out based on certain criteria or considerations (Sugiyono, 2023), such as consumers who have shopped at Matahari Department Store in Palu City. Because the total population is unknown, the method for calculating the sample size is the Unknown population formula using the Lemeshow formula:

Table 1. Lemeshow Formula

$n = \frac{Z^2 \cdot P \cdot (1 - P)}{d^2}$ $n = \frac{1,96^2 \cdot 0,5 \cdot (1 - 0,5)}{0,1^2}$ $= \frac{3,8416 \cdot 0,5 \cdot (0,5)}{0,01}$ $= \frac{0,9604}{0,01} = 96,04$	<p>Information:</p> <p>n = number of samples</p> <p>z = z score corresponding to the desired confidence level. The standard for 95% confidence is 1.96</p> <p>p = unknown population proportion (0.5)</p> <p>d = margin of error or permissible level of error (0.1 for 10%)</p>
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Source: Processed Researcher Data (2025)

Thus, a sample of approximately 96 respondents is required for this study, with an unknown population size. The data analysis method is multiple linear regression analysis, which is used to test or describe the relationship between the independent and dependent variables, and is processed using SPSS.

Research Instrument Testing

The test was conducted at Ramayana, Palu City, on 30 respondents with 4 variables and a total of 27 statements. All statement indicators from the Discount (X1), Brand Image (X2), Brand Trust (X3), and Consumer Satisfaction (Y) variables had an r-value greater than 0.361 (r-table), so all indicators were declared valid. Furthermore, a reliability test was carried out using the Cronbach's Alpha value, and the results showed that all variables had a value of more than 0.60, so it can be concluded that this research instrument is reliable.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Respondent Data Characteristics

This study involved 96 respondents. Respondents collected by researchers based on gender, age, occupation, income, frequency of shopping at Matahari Department Store in the last 6 months, and product categories that are often purchased. The data collected based on the characteristics of Matahari Department Store respondents, namely: based on gender, dominated by women as many as 53 (55.21%). The majority of respondents are in the age range of 17-25 years, namely 60 people (62.50%). Respondents' occupations are dominated by students as many as 42 people (43.75%), then private employees 19 people (19.79%), entrepreneurs 14 people (14.58%), others 15 people (15.63%), and civil servants 6 people (6.25%). The majority of respondents shopped at Matahari Department Store 1-2 times in the last 6 months as many as 60 people (62.50%). The most purchased products are men's & women's clothing and shoes & sandals, each 41 people (42.71%).

Figure 1: Respondent Data Characteristics
Source: Processed Researcher Data (2025)

Variable Description

In an effort to understand the results of data processing, this study presents the average value of each respondent's response to the dimensions of the variables used.

Table 2. Results of Variable Description

Variables	Dimensions	Indicator	Average value
Discount	The amount of the price reduction	Discount percentage	4.33
		Price after discount	4.08
	price reduction time	Discount duration	4.02
		Special day discount	4.27
	Product type & payment method	Payment method discount	4.06
		Various types of products	4.05
		Average Total Discount Variable	4.13
Brand Image	Brand <i>strength</i>	Brand information conveyed	4.19
		Brand information remembered	4.06
		Brand message is clearly received by customers	3.89
	Brand <i>Favorability</i> (feeling of liking for the brand)	Customers' positive views of the brand	4.20
		Suitability of product attributes to consumer needs	4.05
	Brand <i>Uniqueness</i>	Brand differentiation compared to competitors	4.03
		Average Total Brand Image Variables	4.07
Brand Trust	Dimension of <i>Viability</i>	The perception that a brand can meet consumer needs	4.19
		The perception that a brand can satisfy consumers	4.08
		Brands provide benefits commensurate with price	4
	Dimension of <i>Intentionality</i>	The feeling of security that consumers feel towards the brand	4.07
		Consumer trust in brands	4.20
			Average Total Brand Trust Variables
Customer Satisfaction	Product quality	The product has good quality	4.33
		The product used is in accordance with consumer expectations	4.08
	price	Price matches product quality	4.04
		Affordability compared to competitors	3.84
	quality of service	Responsiveness	4.16
		Reliability	4.18
		Empathy	4.14
	Emotional factors	The pleasure of using the product	4.14
	convenience	The process of getting the product is easy	4.02
Practical payment process		3.98	
		Average Total Consumer Satisfaction Variables	4.09

Source: Processed Researcher Data (2025)

Based on the table above, it explains that out of 85 respondents gave the highest and lowest average assessments on the following indicators: The discount variable has the highest average value on the discount percentage of 4.33 and the lowest on the discount duration of 4.02. The brand image variable has the highest average value on the customer's positive view of the brand of 4.20 and the lowest on the brand message being clearly received by customers of 3.89. The brand trust variable has the highest average value on consumer trust in the brand of 4.20 and the lowest on the brand providing benefits comparable to the price of 4.00. The consumer satisfaction variable has the highest average value on the product having good quality of 4.33 and the lowest on affordability compared to competitors of 3.84.

Classical Assumption Test

Normality Test

The normality test aims to determine whether the residual data in the regression model is normally distributed or not. The normality test uses the One-Sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test method. If the Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed) value is > 0.05, then the data is considered normal.

Table 3. Normality Test Results

One-Sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test		
Unstandardized Residual		
N		96
Normal Parameters ^{a,b}	Mean	.0000000
	Standard Deviation	2.68269786
Most Extreme Differences	Absolute	.051
	Positive	.048
	Negative	-.051
Test Statistics		.051
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)		.200 ^{c,d}

Source: SPSS Processed Data (2025)

Based on the table above, the value of Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed) is 0.200. Because the significance value is greater than 0.05, the residual data can be stated to be normally distributed.

Multicollinearity Test

The multicollinearity test measures whether there is a high correlation between independent variables that could interfere with the regression model. The benchmarks used are the Tolerance and Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) values. If Tolerance > 0.10 and VIF < 10, then multicollinearity does not occur.

Table 4. Multicollinearity Test Results

Variables	Collinearity Statistics		Information
	Tolerance	VIF	
Discount	0.528	1,894	No Multicollinearity Occurs
Brand Image	0.645	1,551	No Multicollinearity Occurs
Brand Trust	0.590	1,696	No Multicollinearity Occurs

Source: SPSS Processed Data (2025)

Based on the table above, the Tolerance value of all variables is greater than 0.10 and the VIF value is all below 10. So it can be concluded that there is no multicollinearity.

Heteroscedasticity Test

The heteroscedasticity test aims to determine whether there is inequality in residual variance (variety) between observations.

Figure 2: Heteroscedasticity Test Results
Source: SPSS Processed Data (2025)

Based on the image above, the results of the heteroscedasticity test show that the X-axis is labeled “Regression Standardized Predicted Value”, while the Y-axis is labeled “Regression Studentized Residual”. From the results above, it can be stated that there is no heteroscedasticity, because the points on the scatterplot graph are spread randomly above and below the zero axis and do not form any pattern (abstract).

Hypothesis Testing

Multiple Linear Regression Test

Through this analysis, researchers can determine the extent to which discount, brand image, and brand trust variables contribute to consumer satisfaction. Furthermore, multiple linear regression was used to determine the direction of the relationship (positive or negative) and the magnitude of each independent variable's influence on the dependent variable. Therefore, the results of this test are expected to provide a clear picture of the relationship model between the variables studied and serve as a basis for drawing research conclusions.

Table 5. Multiple Linear Regression Test Results

Dependent variable Y = consumer satisfaction					
Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	0.456	2,890		0.158	0.875
Discount (X1)	0.696	0.124	0.435	5,600	0,000
Brand Image (X2)	0.293	0.130	0.158	2,250	0.027
Brand Trust (X3)	0.782	0.149	0.386	5,248	0,000
R = 0.841 F = 74.104					
R Square = 0.707 Sig. F = 0.000					

Source: SPSS Processed Data (2025)

Based on table 5 above, the results of the multiple linear regression test are as follows:

1. It is known that the discount variable (X1) has a regression coefficient value of 0.696. This means that every 1 unit increase in discount will increase consumer satisfaction by 0.696 units. The t-value of 5.600 is greater than the t-table (1.661) and the significance value of 0.000 is less than 0.05. Thus, it can be said that H1 is accepted, which indicates that Discounts have a positive and significant influence on Consumer Satisfaction.
2. The brand image variable (X2) has a regression coefficient value of 0.293. This means that every 1 unit increase in brand image will increase consumer satisfaction by 0.293 units. The t-value of 2.250 is greater than the t-table (1.661) and the significance value of 0.027 is less than 0.05. Thus, it can be said that H2 is accepted, which indicates that brand image has a positive and significant influence on consumer satisfaction.

3. The brand trust variable (X3) has a regression coefficient value of 0.782. This means that every 1 unit increase in brand image will increase consumer satisfaction by 0.782 units. The t-value of 5.248 is greater than the t-table (1.661) and the significance value of 0.000 is less than 0.05. Thus, it can be said that H3 is accepted, which indicates that brand trust has a positive and significant influence on consumer satisfaction.
4. The value obtained from the calculated f is 74.104 with the F table value being 2.704 so that if the calculated F value is greater than the F table ($74.104 > 2.704$), and the significant value is $0.000 < 0.05$ then H4 is accepted and it can be said that simultaneously or together the Discount, Brand Image, and Brand Trust variables have a positive and significant effect on the Consumer Satisfaction variable.
5. The R-square value is 0.707, indicating that 70.7% of the consumer satisfaction variable can be explained by discounts, brand image, and brand trust. The remaining 29.3% is influenced by factors outside the research model.

DISCUSSION

The Effect of Discounts on Consumer Satisfaction

This study shows that discounts have a positive and significant effect on customer satisfaction. Well-designed discounts play a role in increasing consumers' perceptions of value. When consumers perceive added value through discounts, they tend to evaluate the shopping experience more positively and experience satisfaction, or perceive that the benefits outweigh the costs. The substantial discounts offered by Matahari Department Store are able to attract consumer attention and become a key consideration in creating satisfaction. Consumers not only see the discount in nominal terms, but also evaluate whether the final price paid after the discount is truly cheaper and more profitable. Sales promotion strategies such as *seasonal sales*, *clearance sales*, and Matahari Rewards member discounts have proven effective in creating customer satisfaction because they provide a shopping experience that is perceived as more profitable. Consumers feel they are getting quality products at lower prices than normal, resulting in a sense of satisfaction and a tendency to shop again. When consumers find lower prices through discount programs, they feel satisfied because they feel they are getting a greater benefit than other consumers who buy at normal prices. These results align with Simanungkalit et al. (2022), who showed that discounts can increase satisfaction because consumers perceive a tangible financial benefit. Consumers assess satisfaction based on the balance between what they spend (price) and what they receive (benefits). When the discount offered matches expectations and is perceived as fair, consumers' perceived value increases, thus increasing their satisfaction levels.

The Influence of Brand Image on Consumer Satisfaction

This study shows that brand image has a positive and significant impact on consumer satisfaction. Brand image plays a crucial role in shaping consumer perceptions of the quality and value offered by Matahari Department Store. Brand image plays a crucial role in building an emotional connection between consumers and the company. When consumers perceive that a brand reflects their personal identity or values, they develop a sense of pride, emotional attachment, and trust, leading to higher satisfaction. Consumers have a positive perception of Matahari as a trusted, modern, and relevant retail brand. Well-communicated brand information through promotions, store layout, and marketing communications helps establish a clear understanding of the brand's identity and strengths. When brand messaging is easily understood and consistent, consumers tend to develop positive associations that ultimately increase their liking and trust in the brand. This positive perception directly contributes to consumer satisfaction because they feel confident and comfortable choosing Matahari as a shopping destination.

Matahari's brand image has been shaped through the company's long history as one of the largest and oldest retail chains in Indonesia. Matahari is known as a family-friendly shopping center that offers a wide range of fashion, shoes, and accessories with guaranteed quality and affordable prices. This image is built through the brand's consistency in presenting products that meet the needs of Indonesia's middle-class community. Since its inception, Matahari has consistently projected a professional, modern, and trustworthy image, leading consumers to perceive the company as highly reputable and credible. For the people of Palu City, Matahari's brand image is not only related to its products, but also to a comfortable and enjoyable shopping experience. Research from Ferdiansa et al (2022) This is in line with the results of this study, which confirm that a strong brand image can create a competitive advantage through *emotional value* and positive perceptions of the product. A superior brand image provides a competitive advantage because it creates emotional value that sticks in the minds of consumers. Consumers not only purchase products for their functional needs but also for the positive associations and symbolism of the brand. Therefore, the higher the positive evaluation of the brand, the greater the resulting satisfaction.

The Influence of Brand Trust on Consumer Satisfaction

This study shows that *Brand Trust* has a positive and significant effect on consumer satisfaction. This finding indicates that the higher the level of consumer trust in a brand, the greater the level of satisfaction they feel with the product or service offered. Brand trust also creates an emotional connection between consumers and companies. According to Relationship Marketing theory, trust is a core element in building long-term relationships. Consumers who trust a brand not only judge based on rational aspects such as quality and price, but also feel emotionally connected to the brand. They believe that the brand understands their needs and will not disappoint. Consumers trust Matahari Department Store to provide products that meet their needs, both in terms of quality, variety, and price. This trust is built through consistent shopping experiences, a good brand reputation, and the belief that Matahari always strives to meet the needs of its consumers. When consumers feel that a brand is reliable and understands their needs, they perceive a lower risk of making a purchase.

This sense of security and confidence significantly contributes to satisfaction, as consumers are satisfied not only functionally but also psychologically. Consumers believe that the products sold are authentic, meet high quality standards, and are supported by adequate after-sales service. This trust is also shaped by Matahari's reputation as a large, long-established retail chain with high credibility in the eyes of the Indonesian public. This trust, in turn, helps consumers feel secure in making transactions because the risk of purchasing is perceived as very low. Strong brand trust also reflects the company's perception of integrity and consistency in delivering on its promises to customers. When promises communicated through promotions, service, and product quality are truly fulfilled, consumers perceive the brand as a trustworthy entity. In a modern retail context like Matahari, maintaining consistency between expectations and reality is a crucial factor in maintaining customer satisfaction. These findings support the research of Ihsan & Sutedjo (2022), which showed that brand trust significantly increases satisfaction by fostering a sense of security and psychological attachment between consumers and the brand. High trust in a brand makes consumers feel that the brand is reliable and has good intentions in meeting their needs.

The Influence of Discounts, Brand Image, and Brand Trust on Consumer Satisfaction

This study shows that Discounts, *Brand Image*, and *Brand Trust* have a positive and significant effect on consumer satisfaction. These findings indicate that an integrated marketing strategy involving discounts, positive brand image development, and increased brand trust can create a satisfying shopping experience for consumers. Discounts provide direct economic benefits that increase perceived value, while a strong brand image builds emotional attachment and consumer pride in the brand. On the other hand, brand trust creates a sense of security and confidence in the quality of the products and services provided by the company. When these three factors work synergistically, the shopping experience becomes more enjoyable, profitable, and trustworthy, which ultimately increases overall customer satisfaction. The simultaneous research conducted in this study does not support previous research. This shows that this study provides a new contribution to the development of marketing science, particularly regarding an integrated model that simultaneously examines the influence of discounts, *brand image*, and *brand trust on consumer satisfaction*.

CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTIONS

Conclusion

This study found that Discount, *Brand Image*, and *Brand Trust variables* positively and significantly influence customer satisfaction at Matahari Department Store in Palu City. The implementation of promotional strategies such as discounts has been proven effective in improving the shopping experience and customer satisfaction, especially for young age groups who are very responsive to price promotions. In addition, a positive brand image strengthens consumer confidence in the quality and reputation of the store, thereby increasing satisfaction. High brand trust creates a sense of security and reduces purchasing risk, which also strengthens consumer satisfaction. These results emphasize the importance of marketing strategies that include providing discounts, building a positive brand image, and increasing customer trust to increase consumer satisfaction and loyalty in the retail industry. A comprehensive and integrated marketing strategy is expected to increase customer satisfaction, which will ultimately have a positive impact on business performance and the company's sustainability in the future.

Suggestion

Based on the results of the research that has been conducted, suggestions that can be given to increase Consumer Satisfaction at Matahari Department Store, Palu City, are as follows:

1. Matahari Department Store is advised to maintain or increase the variety of longer discount durations, especially during certain periods such as weekends or holiday seasons.
2. The brand's uniqueness needs to be continuously strengthened through innovative product designs, distinctive store layouts, and marketing campaigns that highlight Matahari's local values and brand identity. These distinctive characteristics will serve as differentiators that strengthen the brand's positive image in the eyes of consumers.
3. Matahari must continue to maintain a balance between price and product benefits by ensuring quality is maintained across all product lines. Transparency regarding quality and promotions is also crucial to ensure consumers feel confident that the price they pay is commensurate with the value they receive.
4. To maintain the perception of affordability, Matahari can implement competitive pricing strategies such as product bundling or loyalty programs that provide additional discounts for loyal customers.

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THE EFFECT OF DISCOUNTS, BRAND IMAGE, AND BRAND TRUST ON CONSUMER SATISFACTION AT MATAHARI DEPARTMENT STORE IN PALU CITY

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